

Grains were air-dried and weighed, and yield calculated, leaving a 30-cm border around each plot.

Disease incidence and yield at different seed rates are given in the table. The expected yield increase with higher

plant densities was not found. Higher disease incidence affected yield. □

Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Persistent toxicity of three modified formulations of carbofuran to brown planthopper (BPH) in India

M. A. Salam, T. B. Mathew, V. K. Sasidhar, and N. M. Das, College of Agriculture, Vellayani, Trivandrum 695522, India

The Regional Research Laboratory (Hyderabad, India) supplied polyethylene-based and lignin-based formulations of carbofuran reported to be slow releasing in nature. We studied their persistent toxicity to BPH compared to that of commercially available encapsulated granules of carbofuran in a confined cage experiment Jun-Jul 1985.

The treatments were in a factorial combination of 3 formulations of carbofuran (polyethylene-based, lignin-based, and encapsulated) and 2 application rates (0.75 and 1.50 kg ai/ha).

The formulations were broadcast into the floodwater at 0.75 and 1.5 kg ai/ha 5 d after transplanting (DT). Starting 3 d after treatment, toxicity was monitored weekly using the BPH bioassay technique.

Toxicity of polyethylene-based and

Mortality of BPH adults, at various days after treatment, on rice plants in fields that received modified formulations of carbofuran at 2 rates. Trivandrum, India, 1985.

encapsulated preparations persisted at a higher level and longer than did toxicity of the lignin-based granule (see figure). Mortality remained consistently higher with 1.5 kg ai/ha to 50 DT.

The persistent toxicity differed with rate of application, with a significant interaction between formulation and rate of application.

Mortality decline (4.7% /d) was lowest with the polyethylene-based formulation at 1.5 kg ai/ha, closely followed by polyethylene-based formulation at 0.75 kg ai/ha and encapsulated formulation at 1.5 kg ai/ha. Mortality declined at a faster rate in the lignin-based formulation. Release of the active ingredient appeared to differ with formulation. □

Epidemiology of rice tungro virus (RTV) in 1984-85 kharif, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu

M. Subiachandraselvan, R. Saroja, and T. B. Ranganathan, Rice Research Station, Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

During 1984-85 kharif (May-Aug) the rice crop in Chingleput District was completely devastated by an unprecedented outbreak of RTV. Crops planted early the next season

(samba, Sep-Jan) were also severely affected.

We studied the epidemiology of the disease in a field experiment, laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Nine plantings of 25-d-old CO 43 seedlings were staggered at 10-d intervals starting 10 Aug 1984. Seedlings were transplanted in 3- × 3-m plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Recommended agronomic practices were followed and 100-50-50

kg NPK/ha applied. All the P₂O₅ and K₂O were applied basally along with 50% N. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 15 and 30 d after transplanting (DT).

RTV incidence was assessed at 45 DT. The number of green leafhoppers collected in light traps Aug-Nov was recorded by month.

RTV incidence in the field correlated positively with the field population of the vector *Nephotettix*

virescens (see table). The early-planted crops were significantly more severely infected with RTV, resulting in lower grain yield, than late planting. Severe RTV infection in the early samba crop was due to overlapping of younger plants with the sornavari season (May planting) older crop that had high RTV incidence and vector population. When the vector population declined later, RTV incidence also was reduced. We concluded that the spread of RTV was mainly influenced by the vector population. □

Effect of planting time and field population of green leafhopper on RTV incidence.^a Tirur, India, 1984.

Planting date	RTV incidence ^b (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	GLH in light trap (no./mo)
10 Aug	68.6 g	0.97 e	Jul : 181,196
20 Aug	60.6 f	1.77 d	Aug : 30,343
30 Aug	19.6 e	2.60 c	Sep : 2,407
10 Sep	8.1 d	2.43 c	Oct : 906
20 Sep	1.9 c	4.27 a	Nov : 1,278
30 Sep	2.1 c	3.60 b	
10 Oct	1.0 b	2.57 c	
20 Oct	1.2 bc	2.57 c	
30 Oct	0.2 a	2.47 c	
CD (P = 0.05)	1.95	0.36	

^a Means in a column followed by a common letter are not statistically significant at the 5% level.

^b Mean of 3 replications.

A new annelidan pest of rice in Nepal

S. B. Pradhan, Entomology Division, Khumaltar, Nepal

A new pest of rice, tentatively named "Sano Gadeula" (small earthworm), was recorded in farmers' fields during the 1980 crop in the plains and hills of Nepal (see figure). The pest was identified in Japan as *Limnodrilus* sp., phylum Annelida and class Oligochaeta.

Fields infested with this pest

resemble Zn-deficient plots. Leaves of infested plants turn yellow or brown and the plant is stunted. Severely infested plants die.

Closer observation revealed newly hatched worms in the basal part of the plant tissue. Mature worms usually were found in clusters in the roots and the underground basal parts of the plant.

Feeding habits of the worm and plant injury are under study. The worm can survive in fresh water for several days, even without soil, but when exposed without water or soil,

Limnodrilus sp., a new pest of rice found in Nepal.

dies within a minute because of dehydration. □

Caseworm (CW) preference for vegetative stage rice

N. Chantaraprapha, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand; and J.A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IIRRI

CW *Nymphula depunctalis* moths oviposit on the undersides of leaves floating in water. In a no-choice test, most eggs were laid on floating leaves, a few on erect leaves, and some on leaves bent in water (Table 1).

In 13 plots exhibiting all plant growth stages, we randomly sampled 20 hills per growth stage and recorded the number of leaves touching the water. Only vegetative stage rice had significant numbers of leaves in contact with water.

A free-choice test measured

oviposition by seedling age. Potted plants of different ages were immersed in a drum filled with water set so that leaves of each age were at the same distance above the water surface. The number of eggs laid on seedlings 1, 2,

3, 4, and 5 wk after sowing did not differ.

A preference to oviposit on leaves 2, 4, 6, and 8 mm wide was tested.

Excised 4-wk-old floating leaves were randomly pinned to submerged stakes

Table 1. Ovipositional preference of *N. depunctalis* on IR36 rice at different plant ages.^a IIRRI greenhouse, 1983-84.

Plant age ^b (WT)	Oviposition site ^c (no. eggs/10 females per 3 d)		
	Excised floating leaves	Leaves bent in water	Erect leaves
2	123 b	157 a	85 a
4	378 a	189 a	157 a
6	278 ab	153 a	37 b
8	201 ab	179 a	35 b
10	109 b	90 a	31 b
Mean	218	153	69

^a Av of 6 replications, 10 females and males per replication. Potted plants and excised leaves were placed in mesh-covered 44-gallon gasoline drum cages 3/4 full of water. Floating and bent leaves were pinned to submerged stakes. ^b Transplanted 3 wk after germination. WT = wk after transplanting.

^c In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level.